

TO STUDY THE MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF THE GINGER PLANT.

Tursunova Solikha Zafar qizi
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute

Abstract: Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) is a rhizome of the Roscoe family. Zingiberaceae and used as food, spice, supplement and medicine. Ginger has been used in traditional medicine for over 3000 years. Ginger has a number of properties such as pungency, aroma, nutrients and pharmacological activity. Ginger and ginger extracts are known to have many wide-ranging effects.

Key words: Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), gingerols, shogaols, paradols, zingerone, cineole, geraniol (Citril), limonene.

Introduction: Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) is a rhizome of the Roscoe family. Zingiberaceae and used as food, spice, supplement and medicine. Ginger has been used in traditional medicine for over 3000 years. Ginger has a number of properties such as pungency, aroma, nutrients and pharmacological activity.[1,2,3]

Ginger and ginger extracts are known to have many wide-ranging effects. These include fighting against colds, inflammation, bacteria and viruses, fighting against metabolism, fighting against cholesterol in the blood, fighting against several symptoms such as headaches, nausea, indigestion, and diarrhea. known. In addition, the pharmacological properties of ginger

are radioprotective, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, neuroprotective, activity against certain natural, chemical and radiation poisonings. it also has properties such as gastroprotective and protection of the reproductive system. Using these properties, we can find ginger in the composition of many medicines.[4]

The underground stem of the ginger plant, i.e. rhizome, is used for vegetative propagation, in food products and as an additive to medicinal products.[5]

Main part: Ginger rhizomes contain two types of substances, the first is volatile essential oils and non-volatile substances, we can include organic and inorganic substances. In addition, ginger rhizome contains many chemicals, 3%-6% fat, 9% protein, 60-70% carbohydrates, 8% ash, 9-12% water and 2%-3% volatile oil. [3,6,8] These percentages can vary depending on storage conditions (processing, cooking, steaming,) [3] Volatile oils include the following: Sesquiterpenes, such as zingiberine 36%, curcumen 18% and farnesene 10% and monoterpenes such as: cineole 1.3%, borneol 2.2%, geranial i.e. citral 0.8% [6] Non-volatile components contain the main biological activity. They include ingredients such as: gingerols, shogaols, paradols and zingerone. [6]

The main constituents of ginger and its uses

The name of the component	Application
Monoterpene compounds	
Cinirole	Anti-inflammatory [18] anti-inflammatory, antioxidant [19]
Geranial (Citral)	Aroma, food additive[21] hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory [22]
Limonene	Anti-cancer, anti-viral, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial[23], dissolves gallstones, relieves gastroesophageal reflux, anti-cancer[24]
Linalol	Anti-inflammatory, Anti-cancer, Anti-cancer, Anti-microbial, Anti-depressant, Neuro-protective [26]
a/b – Pinene	Taste[27] silogenic, gastroprotective, cytoprotective, antidepressant, antioxidant, antipancreatic, antihypertensive[28]
Sesquiterpene compounds	
b- Elemene	Anti-cancer [29.31]

a- Zingiberen	Anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, [29]
Farnesene	Solvent, emollient, vitamin biofuel [32]
Zerumbone	Anticancer, [33,34] antibacterial, fragrance [35]
Phenolic compounds	
Gingerol	Anti-cancer [39-41] anti-inflammatory and antioxidant [42] antioxidant anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial.
Shogaol	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-emetic.[43,44]
Paradol	Anticancer[46,47] cardioprotective, neuroprotective[48]
Zingerone	Anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anti-diarrheal, anti-spasmodic, anti-cancer, anti-emetic, anti-radiation, anti-microbial [49]
Diarylheptnoid compounds	
Curcumin	Antioxidant, anti-ulcer, anti-cancer, anti-emetic, anti-malarial, anti-microbial [51,52,53]
A mixture of other chemicals	
Essential oil	Bactericidal, antiviral, antiparasitic, insecticidal, analgesic, sedative, anti-inflammatory.[54]
Powder of ginger extract	Anticancer, [2,41] anti-inflammatory, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, antidiabetic[44]

Biological effects of ginger components.

Monoterpenes from the components of ginger (Borneol, Campene, Cineola, α -Pinene, β -Pinene, Geranial (Citral), Linalool, Limonene, β -Phellandrene). Monoterpenes, i.e. terpenes, are characterized by the isoprene unit (C5) and give the plant a pleasant smell and a bitter taste. Monoterpenes have a (C10) skeleton with a carbon skeleton consisting of two isoprene units.

Cineole

Cineol (also called 1,8 cineol or eucalyptol) is a cyclic ether. It is found as part of the main essential oil obtained from *Eucalyptus globulus*. Cineol has anti-inflammatory, anti-inflammatory, anti-hypertensive, antispasmodic, analgesic and anti-anxiety effects.

known. [18,19]

Geranial (Citral)

Geranial (Citral) is a food additive used as a safe flavoring agent. This substance has a hepatoprotective and anti-inflammatory effect.

Limonen

Limonene is a cyclic monoterpene. This substance is a major component of the oil in the peel of citrus fruits and has anti-cancer, antiviral, anti-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial properties.[23] dissolves gallstones, relieves gastroesophageal reflux and is an anti-cancer agent.

Linalool is a terpene alcohol found in plants with two enantiomeric forms. This substance has anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, antiviral, antimicrobial, and antidepressant effects.[26]

Pinene is a bicyclic monoterpene used as a flavor source. [27] There are two isomers of pinene, alpha pinenes.

Pinenes have cytotoxic gastroprotective, anxiolytic, cytoprotective neuroprotective, antioxidant, antipancreatitis and antihyperthermia effects.[29]

Sesquiterpenes. Sesquiterpenes are characterized by three isoprene units with carbon atoms of C-15. Substances belonging to this group are used for aroma and taste purposes.

β -Elemene is one of the stereoisomers in the group of cycloisoprenes. β -Elemene is widely used as an anticancer agent.[29,31]

Farnesene consists of six isomers and can be found in plant esters. But in industry, this substance is used as a main source of solvents, emollients and vitamins.[32]

Zerumbone belongs to the group of cyclic sesquiterpenes. This substance is widely used as an antibacterial and deodorant agent.

Zerumbone belongs to the group of cyclic sesquiterpenes. This substance is widely used as an anti-cancer agent and deodorant agent.[33,34,35]

Phenolics - this substance is distinguished by the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group found in the root of our plant, this substance occurs naturally in the root of the plant and contains polyphenols, which are an important part of bioactive compounds.[36,37]

In addition to the volatile oil belonging to the group of terpenes, we can include phenolic substances and their derivatives as non-volatile components that give ginger its pungency. Among these substances we can include gingerols, shogaols and paradols. [38]

Gingerols are one of the main substances in the rhizome of ginger, and we can give examples of gingerols 6 and 10.[38] 6- Although gingerol is the main gingerol in the rhizome of ginger, we can also find other types of gingerols in the root. 8- gingerol 10- gingerol 12- includes gingerol. Gingerols have anticancer,[39]

anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, neuroprotective[44], antiemetic, and antioxidant properties. [41,42]

Shogaols are substances belonging to the group of phenolics found in ginger root. Shogaols are antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer and anti-emetic substances.[43]

Paradol has anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, cardioprotective and neuroprotective effects [46,47,48].

Zingerone is not present in fresh ginger, but can be formed from gingerols through a retroaldol reaction when ginger is dried or roasted. It is known from the literature that this substance has various effects and activities, such as anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anti-diarrheal, anti-spasmodic, anti-cancer, anti-emetic, radiation protection, antimicrobial, appetizing.

Diarylheptanoids consist of two aryl groups connected by a heptane chain and are divided into linear and cyclic groups. These substances are also found in the rhizome of ginger. We can include Curcumin, DihydrogingeroneA, Gingerone D in this group of substances. These substances have antioxidant, anti-ulcer, anti-cancer, cardioprotective, anti-diabetic, anti-malarial, anti-microbial, neuroprotective effects.

Conclusion: In this analysis of the literature, the composition of the rhizome of the ginger plant and its use in the field of medicine and pharmaceuticals were studied. In addition, the chemical composition of the rhizome of the ginger plant and the importance of each substance were studied.

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